

CHARACTERIZATION OF METHYLOBACTERIUM SPP. POPULATION, ENDOPHYTES OF OLIVE SAPWOOD

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Endophytic bacteria are of biotechnological and agronomic interest as they promote plant healthiness. Investigations on the bacterial endophytic population occurring into the xylem of healthy and *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* (*Xfp*) infected olive trees showed that under field conditions, the population level of cultivable endophytic bacteria is highly variable, being mainly affected by the host genotype, host age, and wilting severity. Among the different groups, the cultivable microbial community of olive trees, either infected or not by *Xfp*, are *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Lysinibacillus*, *Pantoea*, *Microbacterium*, *Stenotrophomonas*, and *Methylobacterium* spp. Bacteria of the genus *Methylobacterium* are facultative methylotrophs, and different species are endophytes in a variety of plants. As endophyte they promote plant growth and root formation by producing phytohormones and stimulating germination, enhance plant systemic resistance, supply or mobilize nutritional elements (siderophores production), and some species have also been reported as antagonist of bacterial and fungal phytopathogens. Several studies focused on *Methylobacterium* spp. community, which occupy the same ecological niche of *Xfp* in xylematic vessels of citrus plants. Buffered Charcoal Yeast Extract Agar (BCYEA) and Methanol Mineral Salts Agar (MMSA) behaved better than other microbiological media in estimating the population of spp. in the olive sapwood, and data indicated a higher population density in *Xfp*-infected olive sapwood than in the healthy ones, although without any statistical significance. Species of *Methylobacterium* have been reported as potential biocontrol agents, but it depends on which species. *M. extorquens* has a synergistic action, favoring the growth of *Xfp* and increasing the symptoms severity on citrus; conversely, the presence of *M. mesophilicum* reduce the growth of *Xfp* and consequently the symptoms severity. Colonies are pink to light red, circular and smooth with non-pigmented after growth on MMSA, for 6 days at 30°C. The analysis of 16S rRNA gene sequence and phylogenetic data by comparison with ten reference strains, showed that isolates GR18, GR19, GR22 and GR23, obtained from *Xfp*-infected olive tissues, cluster both with *M. fujisawaense* and with *M. radiotolerans*. Therefore, these isolates shows few differences to clearly discriminate the species. *M. radiotolerans* was also isolated from citrus plants infected by *Xfp* in Brazil, but no information about the effects on the pathogen are available. Further research are in progress to better characterize the different *Methylobacterium* strains, using molecular and biochemical approaches, and evaluating *in planta* their activity on olive quick decline syndrome.